

Professional responsibility of the pharmacist in chronic pharmacotherapy: Ethical and economic perspectives

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Abstract

Chronic pharmacotherapy poses significant challenges for contemporary pharmaceutical practice due to its long-term nature and dependence on sustained patient engagement. Medication non-adherence remains a major cause of suboptimal therapeutic outcomes and increased health care costs, highlighting the growing importance of pharmaceutical care.

This article presents a narrative and conceptual review of the professional responsibility of the pharmacist in chronic pharmacotherapy, focusing on medication adherence as a key ethical and economic dimension of pharmaceutical practice. Professional responsibility is conceptualised as a longitudinal and shared process embedded in routine pharmaceutical care, extending beyond regulatory compliance.

The analysis also addresses the impact of digital health technologies on pharmaceutical practice, emphasising the continuing role of professional judgement and accountability. The article affirms the pharmacist's position as a key professional actor in long-term medication management and health system sustainability.

Keywords

Chronic pharmacotherapy, medication adherence, pharmaceutical care, pharmacoeconomics, professional responsibility

Introduction

The global epidemiological shift towards chronic non-communicable diseases has fundamentally transformed contemporary health care systems. Conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, chronic respiratory disorders and neurodegenerative diseases require continuous pharmacotherapy over extended periods, often lifelong (Sabaté 2001; WHO 2003). In this

context, the effectiveness of pharmacological treatment is increasingly determined not only by the properties of medicines themselves, but also by the manner in which therapy is managed, monitored and sustained over time (Vrijens et al. 2012).

Chronic pharmacotherapy differs substantially from acute treatment regimens. It presupposes continuity of care, repeated professional interactions and long-term patient engagement (De Geest et al. 2018). Medication use therefore

becomes a longitudinal process rather than a single clinical act. Within this process, medication adherence has emerged as a critical determinant of therapeutic success, health outcomes and health system sustainability (WHO 2003; Osterberg and Blaschke 2005; Marcum et al. 2017).

Medication non-adherence is widely recognised as a major public health problem, associated with increased morbidity, preventable hospitalisations, reduced quality of life and substantial economic burden (McGivney et al. 2007; Cutler et al. 2018). Despite the availability of effective medicines, many patients with chronic diseases do not follow prescribed pharmacotherapy as intended (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005). These challenges have highlighted the limitations of product-centred approaches and reinforced the importance of pharmaceutical care as a patient-oriented professional practice (Hepler and Strand 1990; van Mil et al. 2004; Cipolle et al. 2012).

Over recent decades, the role of the pharmacist has evolved accordingly. Contemporary pharmaceutical practice increasingly emphasises patient counselling, monitoring of medication use, identification and prevention of drug-related problems and collaboration with other health care professionals (Wiedenmayer et al. 2006; Cipolle et al. 2012; Elliott et al. 2016). Within this expanded role, the pharmacist is positioned as a central professional actor in chronic pharmacotherapy, contributing to both clinical effectiveness and patient safety (FIP 2016).

Against this background, the concept of professional responsibility gains renewed relevance. In chronic pharmacotherapy, responsibility cannot be reduced to legal accountability or regulatory compliance. Rather, it encompasses ethical commitment, professional judgement and sustained involvement in the therapeutic process (Hepler and Strand 1990; Cipolle et al. 2012). Importantly, responsibility in this context is shared across time and among health care actors, with the pharmacist occupying a distinctive and increasingly visible role (van Mil et al. 2004; Garcia-Cardenas et al. 2018).

Materials and methods

This article is based on a narrative and conceptual review of the scientific literature on chronic pharmacotherapy, medication adherence, pharmaceutical care, and professional responsibility. Relevant publications were identified through systematic searches of major bibliographic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, using combinations of keywords related to pharmacist responsibility, medication adherence, pharmacoconomics, and digital health.

Priority was given to peer-reviewed articles, international guidelines, and authoritative reports published in English. The selected literature was critically analyzed and synthesized to develop an integrated conceptual framework addressing the ethical and economic dimensions of pharmacist responsibility in chronic pharmacotherapy. No original empirical data were collected or analyzed.

Chronic pharmacotherapy and medication adherence: a pharmaceutical perspective

Medication adherence is commonly defined as the extent to which a patient's medication-taking behaviour corresponds with agreed recommendations from a health care professional (Vrijens et al. 2012). In chronic pharmacotherapy, adherence encompasses treatment initiation, implementation and persistence over time (Vrijens et al. 2012; De Geest et al. 2018). From a pharmaceutical perspective, adherence is a dynamic process influenced by multiple interacting factors rather than a static patient characteristic (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005).

Research in pharmaceutical science has identified numerous determinants of non-adherence, including therapy-related factors such as complex dosing regimens, polypharmacy and adverse drug reactions; patient-related factors such as beliefs about medicines and health literacy; and system-related factors including access to medicines and continuity of care (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005; Bingham et al. 2020). Many of these determinants fall within the scope of pharmaceutical care interventions (Cipolle et al. 2012; Elliott et al. 2016).

Drug-related problems are particularly prevalent in chronic pharmacotherapy and represent a major source of therapeutic failure (Isetts et al. 2008; Cipolle et al. 2012). Pharmacists are uniquely positioned to identify and address these problems through regular patient contact, medication review and follow-up (Elliott et al. 2016). Consequently, medication adherence emerges as a shared outcome of pharmaceutical care rather than an isolated patient behaviour (Hepler and Strand 1990; van Mil et al. 2004).

Professional responsibility in pharmaceutical care: conceptual foundations

Professional responsibility in pharmaceutical care has traditionally been associated with accurate dispensing and regulatory compliance (Hepler and Strand 1990). However, contemporary practice reflects a broader understanding of responsibility, encompassing professional judgement, ethical commitment and continuity of care (van Mil et al. 2004; Cipolle et al. 2012).

Within pharmaceutical care models, responsibility unfolds over time through repeated professional interactions, monitoring activities and therapeutic adjustments (Cipolle et al. 2012). The pharmacist's accessibility and sustained involvement in medication management position the profession as a key contributor to adherence support and optimisation of pharmacotherapy (Elliott et al. 2016; FIP 2016).

Responsibility in chronic pharmacotherapy is inherently shared among health care professionals and patients, yet the pharmacist's role is distinguished by comprehensive oversight of medication use (van Mil et al. 2004; Garcia-Cardenas et al. 2018). This longitudinal engagement

reflects a process-oriented understanding of pharmaceutical care that aligns with international developments in clinical pharmacy and professional standards (Wiedemayer et al. 2006; FIP 2016).

Economic dimensions of pharmacist responsibility in chronic pharmacotherapy

Medication non-adherence in chronic diseases is associated with substantial avoidable health care costs, including preventable hospitalisations, disease progression and inefficient use of resources (McGivney et al. 2007; Cutler et al. 2018). Pharmaceutical care interventions targeting adherence and drug-related problems have demonstrated favourable clinical and economic outcomes (Isetts et al. 2008; Dalton and Byrne 2017).

Pharmacist-led medication reviews, counselling and monitoring activities contribute to improved persistence with therapy and reduced health care utilisation (Lee et al. 2006; Elliott et al. 2016). From a pharmacoeconomic perspective, responsible pharmaceutical practice represents an investment in health system efficiency and sustainability rather than an additional burden (Dalton and Byrne 2017).

Digital health and the transformation of pharmacist responsibility

Digital health technologies, including electronic prescriptions, shared medication records and digital adherence tools, have enhanced information continuity in pharmaceutical practice (Bates and Singh 2018). These tools support longitudinal oversight of medication use while reinforcing the need for professional judgement in interpreting and contextualising digital information (Hughes et al. 2001; Bates and Singh 2018).

Digitalisation does not diminish professional responsibility; rather, it transforms its expression. Pharmacists remain accountable for integrating technological support into patient-centred pharmaceutical care and ensuring that digital tools enhance, rather than compromise, safety and effectiveness in chronic pharmacotherapy.

Discussion

This analysis conceptualises professional responsibility as a central dimension of pharmaceutical care in chronic pharmacotherapy. Medication adherence is reframed as a shared professional outcome shaped by sustained pharmaceutical engagement rather than patient behaviour alone, with ethical commitment and economic efficiency emerging as mutually reinforcing dimensions of responsible pharmaceutical practice.

From a broader professional perspective, this conceptualisation has important implications for pharmaceutical education and professional identity. As chronic pharmacotherapy becomes the dominant mode of medication

use, pharmacists are increasingly required to integrate clinical knowledge with ethical judgement, communication skills and long-term patient engagement. Understanding professional responsibility as a longitudinal and shared process supports the development of competencies aligned with contemporary pharmaceutical care models and reinforces the role of pharmacists as contributors to continuity of care, patient empowerment and health system sustainability.

In this context, the pharmacist's longitudinal involvement in medication management positions the profession as a key contributor to patient outcomes, while digital health technologies further expand the scope of professional responsibility and underscore the continuing importance of professional judgement and accountability.

As a narrative and conceptual review, this article does not present original empirical data. Nevertheless, it integrates established pharmaceutical literature to articulate a coherent framework for understanding professional responsibility in chronic pharmacotherapy and to provide a basis for future empirical research and professional development.

Conclusion

Chronic pharmacotherapy demands sustained professional engagement and coordinated care over time. Medication adherence highlights the ethical and economic significance of professional responsibility within pharmaceutical practice. The pharmacist's role in supporting adherence, preventing drug-related problems and promoting efficient use of resources affirms the value of responsible pharmaceutical care for both patient outcomes and health system sustainability.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the conception of the manuscript. M.V. developed the conceptual framework of the article, conducted the primary literature analysis and drafted the initial version of the manuscript. A.V. contributed to the critical revision of the manuscript, with emphasis on pharmaceutical practice and professional standards, and provided expert input on the interpretation of the findings. S.V. contributed to the analysis and interpretation of the economic aspects of medication adherence and pharmaceutical care and participated in the critical revision

of the manuscript. T.D. and T.Dim. contributed to the review of relevant literature and provided comments on the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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